

1 **Resistance to *Aspergillus flavus* and *A. parasiticus* in almond advanced**
2 **selections and cultivars**

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Abstract

21

22 Aflatoxins contamination of almond kernels, caused by *Aspergillus flavus* and *A.*
23 *parasiticus*, is a severe concern for growers due to its high toxicity. In California,
24 the global leader of almond production, aflatoxin can be managed by applying
25 the biological control strain AF36 of *A. flavus* and selecting resistant cultivars.
26 Here, we studied the kernel resistance of almond genotypes to *Aspergillus* spp.
27 by inoculation assays. We also examined the protective effects of the shell and
28 seedcoat in preventing aflatoxin contamination. The pathogen showed a meager
29 ability to contaminate in-shell kernels. The seedcoat provided a layer of protection
30 but not complete. In kernel inoculation assays, none of the studied almond
31 genotypes showed a total resistance to the pathogen. Still, nine traditional
32 cultivars (e.g., 'Nonpareil' and 'Sonora') and four advanced selections were
33 classified as resistant. Because these advanced selections contained germplasm
34 derived from peach, we compared the kernel resistance of three peach cultivars

35 to that shown by kernels of a resistant ('Sonora') and a susceptible ('Carmel')
36 almond cultivar and five pistachio cultivars. Overall, peach kernels were much
37 more resistant to the pathogen than almond kernels, which were more resistant
38 than pistachio kernels. Finally, we studied the combined effect of the cultivar
39 resistance and the strain AF36 in limiting aflatoxin contamination. Thus, we co-
40 inoculated almond kernels of the resistant cv. Sonora and the susceptible cv.
41 Carmel with AF36 before (until 72 h) and after (48 h) inoculating with a toxigenic
42 strain of *A. flavus*. The percentage of aflatoxin reduction because of AF36 strain
43 was higher in 'Carmel' kernels (98 %) than in the 'Sonora' ones (83 %) since
44 cultivar resistance also affected the kernel colonization by the biological control
45 strain. AF36 strain limited aflatoxin contamination in almond kernels even when
46 applied 48 h after the toxigenic strain. Our results indicated that cultivar
47 resistance combined with biocontrol offers a promising control strategy.

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50 *parasiticus*

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55 Almond [*Prunus dulcis* (Miller D.A. Webb) syn. *Amygdalus dulcis* Mill., or
56 *Amygdalus communis* L.] is one of the most important tree nut crops in California,
57 where over 80% of the annual global production occurs
58 (<https://www.fas.usda.gov/commodities>). In California, aflatoxins contaminate
59 almond nuts at very low frequencies (Pigłowski 2019). Despite this, aflatoxins are
60 a severe concern for growers since shipments exceeding regulatory thresholds
61 are rejected in domestic and international markets (Whitaker et al. 2010). In
62 Californian nut-growing areas, the species *Aspergillus flavus* and *A. parasiticus*
63 are the predominant producers of aflatoxins (Doster and Michailides 1994;
64 Ortega-Beltran et al. 2019). Generally, the fungus *A. parasiticus* produces the
65 four types of aflatoxins B₁, B₂, G₁, and G₂, while the population of *A. flavus*
66 consists of toxigenic isolates, which produce B₁ and B₂ aflatoxins, and non-
67 aflatoxigenic isolates (Amaiike and Keller 2011).

68 Wild non-toxigenic isolates of *A. flavus* (hereafter referred to as atoxigenic
69 isolates) have allowed the development of aflatoxin biocontrol strategies for
70 numerous crops, including nut crops (Doster et al. 2014). The atoxigenic
71 biocontrol is based on the release of atoxigenic isolates of *A. flavus* to displace
72 the native toxigenic ones (Mehl et al. 2012). Aflatoxin reduction due to the
73 introduction of atoxigenic strains of *A. flavus* increases when the contamination
74 in the target crop is higher (Moral et al. 2020). Although aflatoxin frequency is low
75 for nuts in California, the biocontrol strain AF36 of *A. flavus* (registered for
76 commercial use as Preval™) has been shown to be an effective strategy for
77 reducing aflatoxin contamination in Californian Pistachios (Doster et al. 2014).
78 Similarly, when applied in almond orchards, AF36 strain became the predominant
79 one in the soil and displaced the toxigenic strains of both *A. parasiticus* and *A.*
80 *flavus*. Biocontrol products formulated with atoxigenic isolates as active
81 ingredients have been registered with biopesticide regulatory authorities to
82 protect different crops in the US, Italy, and several African nations
83 (<http://www.agronomico.com/AFX1.aspx>; Moral et al. 2020).

84 The risk of almond contamination by aflatoxins in California mainly stems from
85 the infestation by navel orange worm (*Amyelois transitella*), a Lepidopteran pest
86 whose larvae damage the almond fruit and can serve as a vector for aflatoxin-
87 producers to reach the kernel (Hamby et al. 2011; Palumbo et al. 2014; Wilson

88 et al. 2020). Weather conditions (Williams et al. 2021) and the composition of
89 pathogen populations also influence aflatoxin content in almonds (Ortega-Beltran
90 et al. 2020). Even though different studies have been conducted, there are still
91 gaps in knowledge concerning almond resistance to *Aspergillus* spp. For
92 example, the risk of infestation and contamination of almond by aflatoxins could
93 depend on shell type (paper-shell, soft, semi-hard, or hard shell) and cultivar
94 resistance to the pathogen.

95 In 1994, Gradziel and Wang showed the protective effect of the seedcoat against
96 *A. flavus* colonization (Gradziel and Wang 1994). These authors, and later
97 Dicenta et al. (2003), evaluated the resistance of kernels of various American and
98 European almond cultivars to *A. flavus* through inoculation assays considering
99 the kernel colonization by the pathogen but not the aflatoxin concentration. In
100 2000, Gradziel et al. (2000) evaluated the kernel resistance of 13 almond cultivars
101 and four advanced selections (almond × peach backcrosses) to *A. flavus* by
102 inoculating split kernels and evaluating kernel colonization. The latter study also
103 assessed the pathogen's ability to produce aflatoxin on agar plus almond kernel
104 powder from these almond genotypes (Gradziel et al. 2000). In a more recent
105 study (Gradziel 2020), the author described a marked reduction of aflatoxin
106 content in almond cultivars incorporating peach resistance genes.

107 The studies mentioned above were conducted using the fungus *A. flavus* but not
108 the highly toxigenic *A. parasiticus* (Dicenta et al. 2003; Gradziel et al. 2000;
109 Gradziel 2020). Consequently, it is necessary to evaluate susceptibilities to *A.*
110 *parasiticus* because this species commonly interact with almond (Donner et al.
111 2015). Indeed, *A. parasiticus* is responsible for over 50% of the Californian nut
112 batches exceeding 20 ppb of total aflatoxins [regulatory limit established at the
113 Food and Drug Administration (FDA) in the USA] (Garcia-Lopez et al. 2018).

114 Aflatoxin biocontrol by the AF36 of *A. flavus*, and other atoxigenic strains of the
115 same species, has been previously conducted using a single almond cultivar
116 under controlled conditions (Ortega-Beltran et al. 2019). However, the combined
117 effect of cultivar resistance and *A. flavus* AF36 in limiting aflatoxin contamination
118 in almond kernels has not been studied.

119 The evaluation of the different almond cultivar resistance to both *A. flavus* and *A.*
120 *parasiticus* infection and aflatoxin production was the primary purpose of this
121 study. We also assessed the protective effect of the shell and the seedcoat
122 against pathogen colonization and kernel contamination with aflatoxins and
123 compared the resistance with different peach and pistachio cultivars. Finally, we
124 examined the combined effect of cultivar resistance with biocontrol using the
125 atoxigenic strain AF36.

126 **Materials and Methods**

127 **Resistance of traditional almond cultivars to *Aspergillus* spp.** In 2016, we
128 studied the resistance of 10 commercially Californian almond cultivars to
129 colonization and aflatoxin production by *Aspergillus* spp. (Table 1), considering:
130 i) the cultivar effect, ii) inoculating kernels with or without shell, iii) inoculating with
131 or without the seedcoat, and iv) inoculating with aflatoxin-producing isolates of *A.*
132 *flavus* or *A. parasiticus*. Almond kernels were inoculated with 0.5 ml spore
133 suspension per kernel (10^6 spores per ml of water + TWEEN® 20) (Ortega-Beltran
134 et al. 2018). In all cases, we inoculated 20-24 unshelled kernels and 20-24
135 kernels protected with the shell (henceforth nuts) of each cultivar, set in three
136 replicates (three Petri dishes). Before inoculation, both kernels and nuts were
137 surface-disinfected by immersion first in 10% sodium hypochlorite for 2 min and
138 then in 70% ethanol for 2 min (Camiletti et al. 2018). Almond kernels and nuts
139 were then air-dried for 1 h on an aseptic surface in a biosafety cabinet. Kernels
140 and nuts were independently inoculated with two reference isolates of *A. flavus*
141 (2A1L11 and 29C3L11) and one of *A. parasiticus* (10A1P11) (Ortega-Beltran et
142 al. 2019). A small wound ($\sim 5 \times 5$ mm) was made by scratching the seedcoat of
143 half of the almond kernel group inoculated to evaluate the protective effect
144 reported by Gradziel and Wang (1994). In this case, we studied the effect of
145 wounding on kernels inoculated just *A. flavus* to reduce the number of
146 experimental units. Petri dishes containing the kernels or nuts were incubated for
147 7 days at optimal conditions for aflatoxin production (30°C and 100% humidity)
148 after placing the Petri dishes in humid chambers [plastic containers (22 × 16 × 10
149 cm)]. Colonization (including both amounts of mycelia and sporulation) of each
150 inoculated kernel and nut was quantified using a 0 to 14 scale where 0 = no
151 mycelium and 14 = kernel or nut completely covered with spores (Dicenta et al.

152 2003). In addition, the thickness of the seedcoat of 10 kernels of each almond
153 genotype was measured using a Leica compound microscope (Leica DM2000
154 LED Microscope, Wetzlar, Germany) to determine whether it correlates with
155 resistance to fungal growth. Towards this goal, the kernels were frozen, cut using
156 a microtome (Microtome PFM Medical, Köln, Germany), and mounted on glass
157 slides with sterile water.

158 After assessing the kernel colonization, we followed the method approved by the
159 Association of Official Analytical Chemists (Cunniff 1995) for aflatoxin extraction.
160 Thus 30 ml 60% methanol was added to each kernel set in each Petri plate. The
161 concentration of B₁ and G₁ aflatoxins were evaluated by thin-layer
162 chromatography (TLC) using a CAMAG TLC Scanner 3 (Muttentz, Switzerland)
163 following the protocol described by Camiletti et al. (2018). As a reference for
164 calculations, we employed aflatoxin standards B₁, B₂, G₁, and G₂, from Sigma-
165 Aldrich (St. Louis, MO).

166 **Resistance of advanced selection and cultivar of almond to *Aspergillus***
167 **spp.** In 2016, we used two isolates of *A. flavus* (2A1L11 and 29C3L11) and one
168 of *A. parasiticus* (10A1P11) to evaluate the resistance of kernels of 10 traditional
169 cultivars and nine advanced selections to both fungal growth and aflatoxin
170 accumulation (Table 2). Towards this goal, we inoculated the non-wounded
171 kernels and incubated them in Petri dishes as described above, but with an
172 incubation period of 10 days. Also, we measured the thickness of the seedcoat
173 of 10 kernels of each almond genotype as described above.

174 **Resistance of almond, peach, and pistachio kernels to *Aspergillus* spp.** In
175 previous assays, we observed that almond × peach cultivars (e.g.,
176 'Independence' or selections A05, and 6-340) showed high resistance to
177 *Aspergillus* spp. Therefore, in 2017 we compared resistance to kernel rot and
178 aflatoxin accumulation of two almond and four peach cultivars. Also, for
179 comparison, we included four pistachio cultivars in the assay. In all the cases, we
180 disinfested and inoculated non-wounded kernels using a spore suspension of *A.*
181 *flavus* 2A1L11. The inoculated kernels were incubated for 7 days, and aflatoxin
182 B₁ was quantified as above. The experiment was repeated in 2018. The data of
183 both repetitions were combined after checking for homogeneity of the
184 experimental error by the F test.

185 **Combined effect of biocontrol and cultivar resistance.** In 2017, we studied
186 the combined effect of cultivar resistance with the atoxigenic *A. flavus* isolate
187 AF36, the active ingredient of the biocontrol product AF36 Prevail™, by co-
188 inoculating almonds kernels of cvs. Carmel (susceptible) and Sonora (resistant).
189 We disinfested 10 almond kernels of each cultivar and co-inoculated them using
190 0.5 ml of a spore suspension (10^6 spores/ml) of each the atoxigenic isolate AF36
191 and *A. flavus* toxigenic isolate 2A1L11. There were five treatments: AF36
192 inoculated 72, 48, and 24 h before inoculating the 2A1L11 isolate; 0 h, both
193 isolates simultaneously inoculated; and + 48 h, AF36 inoculated 48 h after
194 2A1L11 isolate was inoculated. We used as controls almond kernels inoculated
195 with only the toxigenic or only the atoxigenic isolate. Kernel disinfestation,
196 inoculation, incubation (for 7 days), and B₁ quantification were performed as
197 above. The experiment was repeated. The data of both experiments were
198 combined after checking for homogeneity of the experimental error by the F test.

199 **Statistical analysis.** We arranged all the assays into a completely randomized
200 design. We subjected data of different independent variables to factorial analysis
201 of variance (ANOVA). When necessary, dependent variables (B₁ or G₁ aflatoxin
202 concentrations) were log- or inverse-transformed for variance homogeneity. After
203 ANOVA, we compared the means by Fisher's protected least significant
204 difference (LSD) at $P = 0.05$. Likewise, we calculated the percentage (%) of the
205 variance attributed to the independent variables calculating eta squared (η^2 , an
206 r-type effect) according to $\eta^2 = [(\text{effect} / \text{SSTotal}) \times 100]$ (Norman and Streiner
207 2008). We classified the cultivars using a non-hierarchical K-Means cluster
208 analysis, in which the initial cluster center method assumed three groups
209 (susceptible, moderately susceptible, and resistant). We used the average
210 concentration of aflatoxins B₁ and G₁ for each combination isolate-
211 cultivar/genotype of inoculated kernels. We selected the optimum number of
212 groups according to the dendrogram's topology for observations of the cluster,
213 testing the significance of the formed group on the aflatoxin accumulations and
214 checking the presence of extreme values and outliers in Box and Whisker Plots
215 (Moral et al. 2017). When almond kernels were co-inoculated with the biocontrol
216 isolate AF36, we separately studied the significance of differences between
217 inoculated and co-inoculated kernels for each cultivar according to the non-

218 parametric test Wilcoxon-Run Test at $P = 0.05$. Finally, we analyzed the
219 relationships between the dependent variables by Pearson's correlation. Data
220 from all experiments were analyzed using Statistix 10 and SPSS 16 Software.

221 RESULTS

222 **Resistance of commercial almond cultivars to *Aspergillus* spp.** Because,
223 seedcoat wounds were made only on almond kernels inoculated with the *A. flavus*
224 isolates, two ANOVAs were independently conducted (Table 1). In the first
225 ANOVA, we omitted the isolate *A. parasiticus* to examine the effect of wounding
226 on kernel contamination by aflatoxin B₁. We found significant effects of the
227 almond cultivar ($\eta^2 = 26\%$ of the total variance), the presence of the wound on
228 the seedcoat ($\eta^2 = 0.12\%$; wounded kernels were more susceptible than intact),
229 and the *A. flavus* isolate ($\eta^2 = 6\%$; 26C3L11 produced more aflatoxin B₁ than
230 2A1L11), while the double and triple interactions were not significant ($P > 0.05$).
231 We obtained similar results according to the kernel colonization, but the
232 interaction wound \times cultivar was significant ($P = 0.006$; $\eta^2 = 5\%$). Furthermore,
233 when we studied the effect of the cultivar on the inoculation conducted using the
234 isolate 10A1P11 of *A. parasiticus* (by omitting *A. flavus*), we found significant
235 differences ($P \leq 0.01$; $\eta^2 > 70\%$) among almond cultivars for the three dependent
236 variables (B₁ and G₁ contaminations; and kernel colonization).

237 Overall, kernels of cv. 'Sonora' produced the lowest aflatoxin concentration (B₁ +
238 G₁ = 60 ppm) but at a similar level than kernels of cv. 'Independence' (B₁ + G₁ =
239 89 ppm). Wounding the seedcoat of kernels of cv. 'Sonora' markedly increased
240 aflatoxin accumulation. The seedcoat thickness ranged from 111 to 157 μm for
241 the cvs. Butte and Independence, respectively. Overall, there was no correlation
242 ($r = -0.308$; $P = 0.501$) between the thickness of the seedcoat and aflatoxin
243 concentration in the non-wounded inoculated kernels of the different cultivars.

244 According to the K-Means cluster, the cvs. Independence, Nonpareil, Sonora,
245 and Wood Colony formed the aflatoxin resistant group, while cvs. Carmel and
246 Frintz were the most susceptible. The remaining four cultivars formed a
247 moderately susceptible group (Table 1). As expected, aflatoxin concentrations
248 (B₁ and G₁) on almond kernels were significantly correlated with fungal
249 colonization ($r = 0.730$; $P < 0.001$).

250 Independent of shell type of (hard, semi-hard, soft, or paper), *Aspergillus* spp.
251 showed a lower ability to grow on the inoculated nuts (i.e., in-shell seeds) and did
252 not produce aflatoxin on the shell (*data not shown*). However, the fungus could
253 overcome the shell barrier and reach the kernel. Even so, the presence of intact
254 shells reduced the aflatoxin contamination by more than 100-fold, and only one
255 experimental unit (one Petri dish with seven 'Sonora' nuts inoculated with *A.*
256 *parasiticus*) showed more than 20 ppb of aflatoxin B₁ (96 ppb).

257 **Resistance of almond advanced selections and cultivars to *Aspergillus***
258 **spp.** There were significant effects of almond genotype ($P < 0.001$; $\eta^2 = 17\%$),
259 *Aspergillus* isolate ($P < 0.001$; $\eta^2 = 6\%$), and their interaction ($P < 0.001$; $\eta^2 =$
260 21%) on aflatoxin accumulation in inoculated kernels. For kernels inoculated with
261 *A. parasiticus*, the almond genotype explained around 65% of the total variance
262 in aflatoxin G₁ content. ANOVA also showed significant differences among
263 almond genotypes ($P < 0.001$; $\eta^2 = 81\%$) and between *Aspergillus* isolates ($P <$
264 0.001; $\eta^2 = 14\%$), while the interaction between both independent variables was
265 not significant ($P = 0.149$). Fisher's LSD classified the *Aspergillus* isolates
266 according to their ability to colonize the inoculated kernels as follows: *A. flavus*
267 29C3L11 > *A. flavus* 2A1L11 > *A. parasiticus* 10A1P11. Kernel colonization was
268 correlated significantly ($r = 0.563$; $P = 0.012$) with aflatoxin concentration.

269 Overall, kernels of the advanced selection A04,8-160 and the Spanish cultivar
270 Tarragona had the lowest aflatoxin concentration (B₁ + G₁ = 159 and 167 ppm,
271 respectively), forming the resistant group with eight other genotypes. Conversely,
272 the advance selections A95,1-26 and A97,1-132 together with the Californian
273 cultivars Aldrich and Price formed the susceptible group (B₁ + G₁ ranged from
274 455 to 346 369). The cvs. Antofñeta, Marta, Marcona, and the advanced
275 selections A4,18-20 and A06,3-319 formed the moderately susceptible group
276 (Table 2). The seedcoat thickness ranged from 88 to 264 μm for the genotype
277 A05,6-340 and the cv. Antofñeta, respectively. Again, there was no significant
278 correlation ($r = 0.196$; $P = 0.4349$) between seedcoat thickness (μm) and fungal
279 colonization.

280 **Resistance of almond, peach, and pistachio kernels to *Aspergillus* spp.**
281 When we evaluated the kernel resistance of cultivars of various crops to aflatoxin
282 B₁ contamination, we detected significant ($P < 0.001$; $\eta^2 = 26\%$) differences

283 among them (pistachio 62 ppm > almond 36 ppm > peach 3 ppm), although there
284 were differences among cultivars of each crop. When we used the cultivars (i.e.,
285 not considering the crop) as the independent variable, it explained 33% of the
286 total variance ($P < 0.001$). Overall, kernels of peach had much lower aflatoxin
287 levels for all cultivars, although the kernels of cv. Ryan Sun had similar levels as
288 those of almond cv. Sonora. In the case of almonds, cv. Sonora had lower
289 aflatoxin B₁ levels than the pistachio cultivars, except cv. Aria (Fig. 1).

290 **Combined effects of aflatoxin biocontrol and cultivar resistance.** As
291 expected, co-inoculated kernels of the cvs. Carmel (previously classified as
292 susceptible) and Sonora (resistant) had significantly (Wilcoxon Rank Test, $P <$
293 0.001) lower aflatoxin concentrations than kernels inoculated just with the
294 toxigenic isolates. For example, kernels of cv. Carmel (used as a positive control)
295 had aflatoxin concentrations between 47 and 116 ppm, while aflatoxin content in
296 co-inoculated kernels of this cultivar was consistently below 15 ppm (1.5 ± 3.6
297 ppm). In the resistant cv. Sonora, these differences were also evident (10 ± 3.8
298 ppm in inoculation with toxigenic *versus* 2 ± 3.3 ppm in co-inoculation with
299 toxigenic and atoxigenic isolates). Considering just the co-inoculated kernels (i.e.,
300 using the percentage of aflatoxin reduction as a dependent variable), we found
301 significant differences ($P = 0.032$) between cultivars. Thus, the percentage of
302 aflatoxin reduction was higher in the susceptible cv. Carmel than in cv. Sonora
303 (98 ± 32 vs $83 \pm 5.4\%$, respectively) (Fig. 2). Conversely, when studying aflatoxin
304 concentration in the co-inoculated kernels, we found no significant effects of the
305 cultivar, AF36 application timing and their interaction. Interestingly, AF36 showed
306 the ability to limit aflatoxin contamination in almond kernels even when applied
307 48h after the inoculation with the toxigenic isolates.

308 **DISCUSSION**

309 To our knowledge, this is the first-time aflatoxin contamination has been
310 evaluated in kernels of various almond cultivars using both *A. flavus* and *A.*
311 *parasiticus*. We found high variability in response to aflatoxin contamination of
312 almond cultivars when inoculated with three *Aspergillus* isolates. This variation
313 agrees with the variability previously described concerning *A. flavus* colonization
314 of almond cultivars (Dicenta et al. 2003). Unfortunately, none of the studied
315 cultivars were immune to either aflatoxin contamination or fungal growth. Dicenta

316 et al. (2003) reported that kernels of several cultivars were completely resistant
317 to colonization by the pathogen even after 18 days of inoculation in conducive
318 conditions. However, we identified exceptional genotypes that that show potential
319 for resistance breeding. Cultivar resistance combined with biocontrol may offer
320 the best strategy for limiting aflatoxin contamination.

321 Our inoculation assays have demonstrated the critical protective effect of the shell
322 in preventing aflatoxin contamination of the kernels, regardless of the type of shell
323 (hard, semi-hard, or paper-shell). However, the type of shell can also affect the
324 susceptibility to other pests. For example, infestation caused by navel
325 orangeworm (NOW), *Amyelois transitella*, a major pest of almond causing kernel
326 damage (wounding) and vectoring the aflatoxin-producing fungi, has been
327 reported as a critical factor in determining aflatoxin contamination (Palumbo et al.
328 2014; Picot et al. 2017). Besides, almond shell-seal and hull-split time have been
329 shown to affect susceptibility to NOW damage (Hamby et al. 2011). Intuitively, it
330 may be expected that lower aflatoxin contamination would occur in cultivars
331 protected by hard shells. However, we have detected low aflatoxin contamination
332 in soft and even papershell almond cultivars in the field. That was the case for
333 'Nonpareil', the most widely grown cultivar across California with 45% State
334 production. This paper-shell variety can be affected by NOW at relatively low
335 levels (Hamby et al. 2011). In our inoculation using unshelled kernels, 'Sonora',
336 another soft-shell widely-grown cultivar, showed low aflatoxin accumulation
337 (Table 1). It should be note that, the latter cultivar showed other fungal
338 contamination problems under field conditions with *Aspergillus* section *Nigri* and
339 *Rhizopus* spp. (T. J. Michailides and J. Moral, unpubl. data).

340 Almond breeding programs utilize peach germplasm to introduce desirable traits
341 into traditional almond varieties (Gradziel 2020). In the first experiment, we
342 included a peach-derived almond variety (i.e., 'Independence') and classified it
343 as one of the most resistant tested cultivars to fungal colonization and aflatoxin
344 contamination. The cultivar Independence is the dominant self-pollinating variety
345 in California, where extensive new orchards of this almond cultivar can be found,
346 and volumes in the market are expected to increase significantly in the upcoming
347 years (Boyd 2020). Likewise, it might be interesting to evaluate the influence of
348 peach genotype rootstocks for conferring aflatoxin resistance to almond cultivars.

349 Nowadays, the rootstock 'Nemaguard' (dominant in traditional San Joaquin
350 Valley almond orchards) provides the attributes of a peach genotype. However,
351 its use is limited in specific agricultural scenarios, such as nematode-infested
352 sandy soils. However, the effect of the almond rootstocks on aflatoxin
353 accumulation has not to be considered.

354 In the second inoculation assay, the Spanish cultivar Tarragona showed
355 considerable resistance to accumulation of both B₁ and G₁ aflatoxins.
356 Interestingly, the pollenizers Winters and Kester, recently released genotypes
357 from the University of California-Davis (Gradziel et al. 2007; Gradziel and
358 Lampinen 2019), showed resistance to aflatoxin accumulation (Table 2). In our
359 study, peach kernels were highly resistant to the pathogen in support of the
360 hypothesis that almond cultivars incorporating peach germplasm are more
361 resistant (Gradziel et al. 2000; Gradziel 2020). This was verified in this study
362 where the highly resistant selections A04,8-160, A05,6-340, A97,2-240, A98,2-
363 305 all contained germplasm derived from peach or wild peach relatives.

364 In contrast, pistachio cultivars were significantly more susceptible than almonds
365 to aflatoxin contamination. Indeed, the pistachio crop is more frequently affected
366 by aflatoxin contamination than almond. For example, from 2010 to 2019,
367 pistachios originated in the U.S. were the nut commodities responsible for most
368 of the notifications according to the European Rapid Alert System for Food and
369 Feed (Alshannaq and Yu, 2021).

370 In our study, the dependent variables aflatoxin contamination and kernel
371 colonization were correlated as was expected. Conversely, Gradziel et al. (2000)
372 did not show any correlation between pathogen colonization and aflatoxin
373 contamination in the kernel. However, these later assays were conducted by
374 inoculating sliced kernels to assess kernel colonization and culture media
375 enriched with the powdered kernel to measure aflatoxin accumulation. These
376 processes do not represent realistic situations.

377 According to our study, the seedcoat of the almond kernel offers a layer of
378 protection (independent of its thickness) but does not provide complete
379 protection. Conversely, cultivar susceptibility to aflatoxin contamination is highly
380 dependent on the shell seal, as reported by Gradziel and Kester (1993). As

381 mentioned above, in our inoculation assays, the pathogen showed meager ability
382 in contaminating kernels when whole nuts were inoculated. Thus, the presence
383 of intact shells in the fruit reduced the aflatoxin contamination by more than 100-
384 fold. These results reinforce the need for adequate control of NOW infestation or
385 the selection of less susceptible almond cultivars to this pest (Palumbo et al.
386 2014).

387 Our results indicate that cultivar resistance combined with biocontrol using
388 atoxigenic isolates offers a particularly promising control strategy. The magnitude
389 of the biocontrol effect was larger in susceptible than resistant cultivars ones
390 since cultivar resistance reduces the kernel colonization by the atoxigenic isolate
391 AF36. Recently, Maxwell et al. (2021) reported aflatoxin degradation by
392 atoxigenic isolates (including AF36) as an additional mechanism through which
393 aflatoxin in treated crops is reduced. Our results further support Maxwell et al.
394 (2021) since we observed a pronounced curative effect of AF36 isolate in co-
395 inoculated kernels.

396 In conclusion, Californian almond farmers would benefit by using genotypes with
397 low susceptibility to aflatoxin-producing fungi and less prone to NOW damage.
398 This resistance strategy can be combined with the currently registered atoxigenic
399 biocontrol AF36 of *A. flavus*. Further reductions could be achieved through
400 standard disease management practices, including on-time harvesting, proper
401 nut drying, sorting-out of damaged kernels, and controlled storage.

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